

Plans for APEX Holography

The surface of the 12-m diameter APEX telescope is sought to be set to an accuracy of ~ 15 micron rms. We intend to carry out near-field holography at 92.4 GHz (3.247 mm) in order to achieve this goal. We will borrow heavily from our experience with SMA holography, where ~12 micron rms has been achieved for the 6-m diameter dishes. Initial work at SMA was done at 92.4 GHz and the current system operates at 232.4 GHz, using the standard SMA receivers. The old 92.4 GHz system will be used for APEX. The strategy is similar to SMA: reposition the subreflector to focus on the near-field transmitter in order to avoid large phase gradients on the 12-m aperture which cannot be easily adequately sampled. With this approach, the required map sizes will be similar to far-field measurements. The plan is to use near-field holography to measure and remove small scale deviations (inter- and intra-panel) and use celestial holography to study large scale deviations. Near-field holography is done at low elevation, for obvious reasons, and therefore measures the dish at unrealistic conditions of gravitational deformation. It is expected that gravitational deformations are large scale whereas panel setting and panel flexure errors are small scale. The fact that there are 5 adjusters per panel implies that any flexure of the panels could be removed (and introduced in the first place, depending on the techniques used during the initial assembly and panel setting process). Near-field measurements will faithfully represent small scale errors, which can then be corrected. With respect to gravitational deformations, to start with we could use a model prediction for the low elevations of the holography measurements and the maps could be appropriately corrected before adjustments are carried out. On a longer timescale, gravitational deformations could be measured using celestial holography and incorporated into panel adjustments.

A system block diagram is shown in Figure 1.

(1) S/N: Ref. Rx

Transmitter power output	10 mW
Transmitter horn gain	20 dB
Range	2500 m
Ref Rx horn aperture	1 cm ²
Ref Rx T_noise	2000 K
holography lock bandwidth	1 kHz

S/N for Ref channel:

$$10 \cdot 10^{-3} / (4\pi \cdot (2.510^5)^2) = 10^{-14} \text{ W/cm}^2$$

$$= -110 \text{ dBm/cm}^2$$

after Tx horn gain

$$= -90 \text{ dBm/cm}^2$$

Noise floor: $kTB = 1.38 \cdot 10^{-23} \text{ J/K} \cdot 10^3 \text{ Hz} \cdot 2000 \text{ K} = 2.7 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ W}$

$$= -126 \text{ dBm}$$

for a 1 cm² horn, S/N = 36 dB : sufficient.

(2) Near-field correction: is a quadratic correction enough?

error term (higher than quadratic term; see Richard Hills' memo)

$$e = [r^2 - 2ru \cos(\phi)]^2 / 8R^3$$

$$r = 6m \text{ (12m dia); } \cos(\phi) \sim 1; u R^n \frac{d\theta}{dt} = 2500 \cdot 0.02 = 56$$

$$e = 2.3 \text{ micron}$$

quadratic correction should do.

(3) refocusing for near-field:

The simulated focus scans show (figs 2 & 3) that for a transmitter range of 2.8 km (Cerro Chajnantor), peak signal is achieved at ~ 8mm (subreflector moved towards the primary). Minimum phase rms calculation suggests an axial subreflector position of 11 mm. Therefore, the available range of +/-15mm subreflector motion is sufficient. It is best if the subreflector is mounted such that the range of axial positions 5-15 mm (from the far-field focus position, towards primary) is accessible.

(3) software:

The data will be acquired on-the-fly from the vector voltmeter. The direct analog outputs will be used through a suitable 2 channel ADC. 12 bit quantization should be sufficient (8 bit should be alright strictly, but we play it safe and allow some flexibility in setting the power levels). The telescope should scan a square raster of adjustable size, at adjustable speed. A data stream of time-stamped encoder values and a data stream of time-stamped vector voltmeter output (amplitude and phase) shall be produced which can be collated and re-gridded off-line onto a regular grid for inversion and processing. An option to visit the bore-sight position periodically during the raster should be available. The on-line software shall be provided by APEX. The details of this software may be discussed if necessary. The data reduction software will be the same as that used at the SMA with appropriate changes to parameters.

(4) Hardware:

A transmitter, a main receiver and a reference receiver are loaned from the SMA, complete with down-conversion electronics to feed the vector voltmeter provided by APEX. The ADC converter shall be provided by APEX. A block diagram of the system is shown in Fig 1. Appropriate mechanical interfaces will have to be provided to mount the reference Rx behind the sub-reflector (viewing the transmitter directly). The main receiver will be mounted at the cassegrain focus. The details of the mounting are shown in figs 4 & 5.

T. K. Sridharan

MAIN RX UNIT

REF. RX UNIT

SMA 3-mm
HOLE BLOCK
T.K. Sridharan

APEX Near-field axial focus curves at 92.4 GHz

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REVISIONS		
ZONE	LTR	DESCRIPTION
1		

Clearance holes for # 2-56 screws.
 8 places, 95.25 (3.750) diameter
 bolt circle

① MAIN Rx MOUNTING

② TRANSMITTER MOUNTING

* the plate should mount flush on the back wall of the transmitter. the transmitter box itself is 19 inch x 14 inch x depth.